

Effect of Total Quality Management on Students' Performance in Chemistry at Secondary Level in Pakistan

Muhammad Siddique, Ijaz Ahmad Tatlah, Muhammad Shabbir Ali, Tajammal Hussain Awan, Hamid Ali Nadeem

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 28, 2021

Accepted:
November 30, 2021

Keywords :

TQM, Students' Performance, Chemistry, Secondary School

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5828015

Abstract

*This study aimed to examine the effect of TQM on students' performance in Chemistry at the secondary level in Pakistan. The quantitative, non-experimental and casual comparative study leads to a positivist paradigm with 200 subjects (male=100 and female=100) selected by the multi-stage sampling technique. Two adapted instruments were used; the first was related to TQM (Töremen et al., 2009), comprised of 16 items with 04 factors; and the second was concerned with Student Academic Performance (Asikhia, 2010) with 18 items and four factors. Standard deviation (SD), t-test, Pearson Correlation, and Regression were run for data analysis. Results show that TQM and students' performance had a strong and positive significant correlation: $r = .778^{**}$, $p < .001$. The results also revealed that TQM had a reasonable power to predict students' performance. It was found that the contribution was statistically significant in explaining the variance in students' performance ($B = .89$, $\beta = .77$, $t = 17.448$, $p = .001$). The R^2 value (0.606) explained the variance in the dependent variable (DV) due to the independent variable (IV). In this case, the variance in students' performance is (60.6%) due to TQM. This study will be helpful for students, teachers, headteachers, and parents. It will give information about the TQM and students' performance at the secondary level, which enhances the intellectual approach of students and teachers for problem-solving during the teaching-learning process. I will overcome the coordination gap among students, teachers, and headteachers. As uncovered in the literature review, only a few research studies have been conducted on TQM and students' performance, especially in the context of science (Chemistry). This study opens new horizons for the researcher to conduct the study at elementary, primary, higher secondary, and higher education levels in the public and private sectors. Experimental, qualitative and mixed-method research may be conducted on the same construct at primary, elementary, higher secondary, and higher education levels.*

Introduction

The current scenario is the age of science and technology in which we live (Habib et al., 2021). Science plays an essential role in every sphere of life; teachers and students own this reality (Rahman Talukder et al., 2021). So, it is a compulsion that students realize the awareness and consciousness of science and technology in the context of performance and quality. In this regard, it is the religious obligation of the individuals that they pay attention to their studies to accomplish a bright career (Mughtar & Mashudi, 2021). So the critical area for the students in science education is to proceed themselves and choose fields like physics, chemistry, biology, etc. According to Shin and Shim (2021), Total Quality Management (TQM) is the prime catalyst to increase quality and performance appropriately. According to Kadhim and Ahmad (2021), TQM is an approach built to enhance quality in science education. It possesses a spinal place in this modern world with enormous receipts (AlOqlah, 2021).

The students' performance is always challenging in education (Tekkumru-Kisa et al., 2021). Students play the spinal role; operational performance could not entertain goals and objectives. Students' performance is imperative in science education, especially chemistry (Ardura & Pérez-Bitrián, 2019; Ramnarain & Ramaila, 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). The critical activity in the students' performance is evaluated. So the TQM and students' performance have close interlink with one another. Quality plays a vital role in improving students' performance in science, especially in chemistry. For better results, it is a compulsion to examine the effect of TQM on students' performance. According to Alzeaideen (2019) and Mahmood and Ismail (2018), TQM enhances students' performance.

Science is considered very vast in the Pakistani context, involving chemistry, Physics, Biology, and Mathematics. Science is regarded as a critical subject from grade 1 to 8. At the secondary level (grade 9th), the examinee has to select the various science streams like Chemistry, Physics, Biology, and Mathematics (Arumugam et al., 2020; Iqbal et al., 2009). Chemistry is taught by different secondary school teachers (SSTs) at the secondary level differently based upon the environmental grounds, cognitive approach, intellectual level, leadership style, which lead to performance. Performance is an exceptional, measurable construct of every entity. Teachers convey information and knowledge while teaching these science subjects, especially in the 9th and 10th grades. In Pakistan, Chemistry is supposed to be a painstaking subject at the secondary level. Students and teachers possessed varying degrees of self-confidence and performance in Chemistry (Bibi et al., 2021; Burns, 1998). (Suleman et al., 2011) argue that teachers use their hidden capabilities, and (Glaveli et al., 2021) explain the information about chemistry among students for better performance.

The curious nature of an individual compels and inspires them for inventions and discoveries. So, they think constructively and critically about new problems in solving them. In this perspective, they question themselves that what is the function of things? What is the reality behind the thing?, how do we overcome the issues, problems, and dilemmas? and how did confidence levels develop in the personals? What is the function of the quality in the perspective of performance? (Avila, 2018; Kershaw, 2003). This study aims to examine the effect of TQM on the students' performance in chemistry at the secondary level. According to Alzeaiden (2019), TQM enhances the students' performance.

The word of quality is derived from the Latin word "*qualis*," which means "*what kind of*"; it is the most complex and challenging concept to define; therefore, it is called slipper concept because it has a vast range of meaning; thus, it is defined in a different concept, context and perspective in various culture and environment (Aljuhani, 2019; Culot, 2019; Oduwaiye et al., 2012). According to Ismail et al. (2017), different issues and problems arise as major hurdles in the smooth flowing of student performance. Alhosani and Yaakub (2020) argue that TQM possesses the central theme and idea for students' participation and satisfaction to obtain quality and performance. TQM plays a vital role in improving and purifying educational institutions' performance globally (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020; Nange & Mkulu, 2020).

TQM is callous, especially in educational institutions; it is challenging to sustain the quality (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020). However, according to Kakuro (2004), the usefulness of 'Science TQM' propagates the trend towards quality management principles, purposed the development of Science TQM and various main beliefs based upon the environmental grounds (Metarfi & Merniz, 2019).

Objectives of the Study

The researcher framed the following objectives as:

1. To examine the effect of TQM on students' performance in chemistry at the secondary level.
2. To investigate the effect of TQM on students' performance in chemistry by gender and academic stream.

Research Questions

Based on the above objectives, the following research questions were formulated:

1. What is the effect of TQM on students' performance in chemistry at the secondary level?
2. Does TQM affect students' performance in chemistry at the secondary level regarding gender and academic stream?

Literature Review

A review of the related literature gives the main crux of the research, which sets the trend and direction of the study. In addition, it provides constructive guidelines to conduct the research study.

TQM is defined as a technique that gives the proper direction to an educational organization for the completion of tasks in the perspective of motivating the individuals, satisfying individuals, praising the collective opinions, and obeying the rule and regulations of government (Altahayneh, 2014; Jermsittiparsert & Sommanawat, 2019; Lunenburg & Fred, 2010; Nange & Mkulu, 2020). TQM is defined in another way as; a conniving initiative that formulates employees' preferred organizations (educational institutions) committed to conform requirements of the individual and desires to permanent progress in the fluency of the organization (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020; Nange & Mkulu, 2020; Nawelwa et al., 2015; Töremen et al., 2009).

According to Zehir et al. (2012) and Burhanuddin and Supriyanto (2018), in educational organizations, like schools, headteachers gain self-confidence when there is regular improvement in the students' academic performance. The TQM philosophy provides the required system for the students to perform outstandingly in the educational context. According to Akhtar et al. (2014); (Seymour, 2018), TQM practices in school help the principals and headteachers produce quality teaching in the classroom. In other words, it is a management philosophy that links up the functions of the educational organization; it focuses on fulfilling the needs (Mkheimer, 2020), requirements, goals, aims, and objectives of students and educational organizations.

De Knop et al. (2004) argue that TQM is over a way of thinking; it very well may be thoroughly examined an appropriate layout utilized in and by educational organizations to guarantee a precise (Nange &

Mkulu, 2020) and suffering advancement of extra worth to capitalize on the acknowledgment of their points. Research studies express TQM as satisfaction, development, participation, and commitment (Anil & Satish, 2019; Mahmood et al., 2014; Suleman & Gul, 2015). According to Raza et al. (2020), the modules of TQM are fundamental expertise bundles to step onwards a valuable help confronted association. The upsides of TQM can be seen as the meaning of its effective execution (Van Kemenade, 2020). Various scholastics have uncovered that the vital goal of TQM is upgrading performance (Elahi & Ilyas, 2019; Hasan et al., 2018).

“Performance enhancement as the top nexus of estimating TQM benefits” (Ekemam & Njoku, 2020). The significant advantages of implementing and accepting TQM are improving satisfaction, superior output, quality of service, and resultantly performance (S Hasham, 2018; Surendran, 2018). According to Sabet et al. (2012), developing output, continuous performance (Abu-Mahfouz, 2019), economic performance (Shafiq et al., 2019), and effective performance are the significant advantages of TQM (Hilman et al., 2019).

The idea of TQM is very emerging and progressive. This idea is accepted in broader management and implementation in different organizations (educational institutions) globally, as this concept came into being in the 1980s (Iyer, 2018; Kuncoro, 2013; Vetchagool et al., 2021). The idea of TQM borrowed from industry, and this concept is implemented in education organizations like schools, colleges, and universities on the intensive demand of stakeholders (Chepkech, 2014; Mukhopadhyay, 2020). According to Suleman and Gul (2015) and Kadhim and Ahmad (2021), several research studies exposed that TQM has been widely time-honored in public and private educational organizations. The overall focus of the TQM in school education is on superior performance (Kaiseroglou & Sfakianaki, 2020). Mahmood et al. (2014) explored that organizations of education had started to comprehend the stress to improve the performance of students and teachers.

Alhosani and Yaakub (2020) argue that the students' concentration and continuous expansion of information are directly related to the teaching-learning procedure at the secondary level. Applying the concept of TQM at the secondary level, it is considered that participation programs guide quality and performance in education through the teaching-learning process (Al-Zahrani, 2015). The practices and guidance are required for all the educational institutions, especially at the secondary level in teaching-learning, furthermore, emphasize the main procedures like teaching-learning process, and it will be efficient as well as regular consideration of performance, which leads by TQM (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020; Alzeaideen, 2019; Aminbeidokhti et al., 2016). Alhosani and Yaakub (2020) suggested that TQM has been engaged in educational institutions in western countries and then in Asian and Arabian countries. According to Suleman and Gul (2015), public sector schools were more rapidly adopting the TQM than private schools (Hilman et al., 2019; Kaiseroglou & Sfakianaki, 2020; Kakingo & Lekule, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

Many researchers conducted the research studies to find the relationship and effect of TQM and performance. It is revealed that TQM and performance are correlated with one another (Mukhopadhyay, 2020). Another research study examined that TQM was positively correlated with students' performance (Samson & Terziovski, 1999). TQM and primary school students' academic performance have a significant relationship (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020). According to Ajayi and Oyeniyi (2017), TQM and students' academic performance positively correlated with one another. Furthermore, a research study explored the positive relationship between TQM and students' academic performance (Sakthivel et al., 2005).

A research study was conducted between TQM and students' academic performance in Iraq and the result as TQM has a positively significant impact on students' academic performance (Zwain et al., 2017). Furthermore, a study was formulated in Iran on the role of TQM and the improvement of students' performance; the study depicts a positive correlation between TQM and students' performance (Malmir, 2013). Similarly, a research study was conducted between TQM and students' academic performance in Nigeria; the results demonstrated the significant relationship between TQM students' performance at the secondary level (Oduwaiye et al., 2012).

The research studies discussed above show that TQM was positively and strongly correlated with students' performance. But, a research study indicated that TQM was weakly correlated with students' performance (Sakthivel et al., 2005).

Methodology

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This study was causal-comparative and quantitative. Data were collected from the subjects using the adapted questionnaire through an online Google form. The research paradigm of this research study was positivism. TQM is an independent variable (IV), while students' performance is dependent (DV). The groups of the elements from which information is collected and applied were called population (Siddique et al., 2021). All the chemistry students of the District Lahore were the population of the study. The selection of the individuals or subjects from the population is called a sample, from which data were collected (Siddique et al., 2021). A multi-stage random sampling technique was used for selecting the subjects due to the pandemic condition of COVID-19. All the chemistry students of district Lahore were the population of this research study. The sample comprised 200 chemistry students (100=male and 100= female) from tehsil City, District Lahore-Punjab, Pakistan. In addition, the sample were also expressed as; 50 male computer students and 50 female computer students, and 50 male biology students and 50 female biology students. This research study was delimited to 10th-grade chemistry students only because they have a better and deep concept of chemistry than the 9th-grade chemistry students (Anwar, 2011).

Instrumentation

The instrumentation plays a vital role in the smooth running of the research (Valverde-Berrocso et al., 2020). Instrumentation is essential for collecting the data from the subjects selected from the population based on a multi-stage random sampling technique (Schratz, 2020). Two adapted questionnaires were used Part A: related to the TQM with 04 indicators as; management support, reaction, empowerment, and continuous improvement with 16 items. Part B: is associated with performance having 18 items with 04 relevant factors like student learning, attendance rate, discipline, and teacher satisfaction. Part one of the questionnaire was adapted from (Töremen et al., 2009), and part two was adapted from (Asikhia, 2010). The responses of the questionnaire are range from strongly agree to disagree strongly.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1

Interpretation of Reliability Test – Cronbach's Alphas

The Cronbach's alpha reliability is applied for checking the consistency of the tool used in this research study. It explains that the value of α for TQM is 0.953, SP is 0.842.

Variables	No. of items	Cronbach Alpha
TQM	16	0.953
SP	18	0.842

Analysis of Reliability

Table 2

Correlation of TQM and Students' Performance

Variables	N	r.value	Sig.
TQM & Students' Performance	200	.778**	.000

$p < .001$ (2-tailed)

Table 2 indicated that the results of Pearson r that TQM and students' performance had a strong and positive significant correlation: $r = .778^{**}$, $p < .001$.

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Table 3
Relationship of TQM Factors with Students' Performance

TQM Factors & Students' Performance	1	2	3	4	5
Management Support	1	.673**	.664**	.228**	.670**
Reaction		1	.660**	.243**	.733**
Empowerment			1	.231**	.738**
Continuous Improvement				1	.295**
Students' Performance					1

$n = 200$, ** $p < .001$ (2-tailed)

Table 3 revealed that the correlation between TQM sub-variables with students' performance. The sub-scales of TQM such as management support ($r = .670^{**}$), reaction ($r = .733^{**}$), empowerment ($r = .738^{**}$), and continuous improvement ($r = .295^{**}$) had positive correlation with students' performance. It was concluded that TQM factors were having significant relation with students' performance.

Table 4
The difference in TQM and Students' Performance on the Bases of Gender

Variables	Gender	N	M	SD	t	df	P
TQM	Male	100	66.87	7.97	3.891	198	.139
	Female	100	62.27	8.73			
Students' Performance	Male	100	76.30	8.32	1.949	183	.001
	Female	100	73.59	11.15			

Table 4 showed that an "independent sample t-test" was run to compare mean scores of TQM and students' performance concerning their gender. It was concluded that TQM had no significant difference concerning students' gender at $p = .139$, but students' performance had a significant difference regarding gender at $P = .05$.

Table 5
"Independent Sample t-test" on Sub-variables of TQM and Students' Performance Based on Gender

Sub Scales TQM & Students' Performance	Gender	N	M	SD	t	df	P
Management Support	Male	100	17.49	2.15	2.58	178	.001
	Female	100	16.50	3.03			
Reaction	Male	100	17.41	2.25	2.515	182	.001
	Female	100	16.46	3.04			
Empowerment	Male	100	17.18	2.17	2.006	180	.003
	Female	100	16.44	2.98			
Continuous Improvement	Male	100	14.79	3.45	4.120	198	.319
	Female	100	12.84	3.24			
Students' Learning	Male	100	21.08	3.28	1.375	192	.005
	Female	100	20.38	3.89			
Students' Attendance	Male	100	20.97	2.77	.789	198	.185
	Female	100	20.64	3.13			
Discipline	Male	100	17.10	2.22	2.076	198	.112
	Female	100	16.37	2.73			
Teachers' Satisfaction	Male	100	17.15	2.12	2.609	179	.016
	Female	100	16.20	2.96			

Table 5 illustrated that an "independent sample t-test" was run to compare the mean score of different sub-scales of TQM and students' performance regarding their gender. The results indicated that three dimensions of TQM, such as management support, reaction, and continuous improvement, significantly differed from four sub-scales. It was also revealed that only two factors of students' performance, such as students' learning and teachers' satisfaction, had a significant difference out of four factors regarding their gender.

Table 6
Differences in TQM and Students' Performance on the Bases of Academic Stream

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Sub Scales TQM & Students' Performance	Academic Stream	N	M	SD	t	df	P
TQM	Computer	100	65.31	9.89	1.211	180	.003
	Biology	100	63.83	7.17			
Students' Performance	Computer	100	74.32	10.44	-.892	198	.384
	Biology	100	75.57	9.34			

In table 6, "An independent sample t-test" was run to see the difference in TQM and students' performance in terms of the academic stream. It was found that TQM had a significant difference based on the academic stream. However, it was concluded that students' performance had no significant difference concerning their academic stream.

Table 7

"Independent Sample t-test" on Sub-variables of TQM and Students' Performance Based on Academic Stream

Sub Scales of TQM & Students' Performance	Academic Stream	N	M	SD	t	df	P
Management Support	Computer	100	16.96	2.77	-.265	198	.415
Reaction	Biology	100	17.06	2.56			
	Computer	100	17.02	2.79	.443	198	.402
Empowerment	Biology	100	16.85	2.63			
	Computer	100	16.61	2.79	-1.077	198	.110
Continuous Improvement	Biology	100	17.01	2.46			
	Computer	100	14.72	3.49	3.801	198	.140
Students' Learning	Biology	100	12.91	3.23			
	Computer	100	20.37	3.95	-1.415	190	.039
Students' Attendance	Biology	100	21.09	3.21			
	Computer	100	20.80	2.84	-.024	198	.457
Discipline	Biology	100	20.81	3.08			
	Computer	100	16.83	2.48	.535	198	.914
Teachers' Satisfaction	Biology	100	16.64	2.544			
	Computer	100	16.32	2.94	-1.935	198	.053
	Biology	100	17.03	2.19			

Table 7 revealed that "an independent sample t-test" was applied to compare the mean scores of TQM and students' performance regarding their academic stream. It was concluded that only one sub-variable of students' performance, such as students' learning, had a significant difference out of four factors. It was concluded that all sub-scales of TQM had no significant difference concerning students' academic stream.

Table 8

Regression Analysis to Identify the Predictive Power of TQM and Students' Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.778(a)	.606	.604	6.23001

a. Predictors: (Constant), TQM

Table 8 (a)

ANOVA to determine the Significance Level of the Predictive Power of TQM to assess Students' Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11815.427	1	11815.427	304.420	.000
	Residual	7684.968	198	38.813		
	Total	19500.395	199			

a. Predictors: (Constant), TQM

b Dependent Variable: Students' Performance

Table 8 (b)
Coefficients Model to Fix the Predictive Power of TQM for Students' Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	17.432	3.326		5.242	.000
	TQM	.891	.051	.778	17.448	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Performance

Tables 8 (a & b) revealed that regression analysis was done to see the effect of TQM on Students' Performance. The results revealed that TQM had a reasonable power of practicably of students' performance. It was found that the contribution was statistically significant in explaining the variance in students' performance ($B = .89$, $\beta = .77$, $t = 17.448$, $p = .001$). The table also illustrated that linear regression results, the R^2 value (0.606), explained the variance in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. In this case, the variance in students' performance is (60.6%) due to TQM.

Discussion

This study had a strong positive correlation between TQM and students' performance and supports that research study conducted by Mukhopadhyay (2020), with findings that TQM and students' performance were correlated. This research supported the study conducted by (Samson & Terziovski, 1999) with results that a positive correlation was found between TQM and students' performance. Similarly, this study was aligned with the study conducted by (Alhosani & Yaakub, 2020), with the main findings that TQM and primary school students' performance have a significant relationship. In the same way, this study also supports the conclusions of Ajayi and Oyeniyi (2017) findings as; TQM and students' academic performance has a positive relationship with one another, and the research study explores the positive relationship between TQM and the academic performance of students (Sakthivel et al., 2005). A research study was conducted between TQM and students' academic performance in Iraq. The research study explored that TQM has a significant and positive impact on students' academic performance (Zwain et al., 2017) as this study has the same findings. A research study was conducted in Iran on the role of TQM and improvement of students' performance which shows a positive relationship between TQM and students' performance (Malmir, 2013) as these findings are aligned with the results of the current study that TQM and students' performance has strong positive correlation. The present study also aligned with analysis conducted by (Oduwaiye et al., 2012) in Nigeria, with the findings as a significant relationship between TQM and students' academic performance at the secondary school level. But, a research study conducted by (Sakthivel et al., 2005) with the findings that TQM has weak relationship with students' performance, and current study negate the results with the previous study as TQM has strong and significant relationship with students' performance. At the end, it is self-evident that the current research supports all previous studies except one. Furthermore, The R^2 value (0.606) explained the variance in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. In this case, the variance in students' performance is (60.6%) due to TQM.

Conclusions

This study shows that TQM and students' performance are interconnected. It is concluded that there is an insignificant difference between male and female students towards TQM, as both male and female students have the same TQM level. Still, the mean difference exists between male and female students in students' performance as male students have better performance than female students. Furthermore, there is a mean difference between biology and computer students in the academic stream, as computer students have more TQM value than biology students. Contrarily, insignificant differences existed between computer and biology students; both computer and biology students have the same performance. As revealed in table 4, in the context of subscales of TQM, management support has a mean difference in male and female students as male students have a higher mean value than female students. Similarly, the reaction has a significant mean difference between male and female students as male students have more meaningful value than female students.

In the same way, empowerment has a significant difference in male and female students as male students have better mean value than female students. In contrast, continuous improvement has insignificant differences between male and female students as both male and female students have the same mean value. It is also depicted in the same table that in the context of students' performance; students' learning has to mean the difference between male and female students as male students possess more mean value than the female students; similarly teachers' satisfaction has a significant difference in mean value as male students possess higher mean value than the female students; contrarily, students' discipline and students' attendance have an insignificant difference in mean value as male and female students have same mean value in this context.

On the other hand, in the academic stream context, TQM factors like management support, reaction, empowerment, and continuous improvement have insignificant differences in mean value as biology and

computer students have no mean difference. In students' performance, the factor, students' learning has a significant difference in biology and computer students as biology students have more mean value than the computer students. Contradictory, the factors students' attendance, students' discipline, and teacher's satisfaction have insignificant difference as computer and biology have no mean difference in this context. TQM and students' performance had a strong and positive correlation: $r = .778^{**}$, $p < .001$. The sub-scales of TQM such as management support ($r = .670^{**}$), reaction ($r = .733^{**}$), empowerment ($r = .738^{**}$), and continuous improvement ($r = .295^{**}$) had positive correlation with students' performance. It was concluded that TQM factors were having a significant relationship with students' performance. It is also concluded that TQM had a reasonable power of practicability of students' performance. It was found that the contribution was statistically significant in explaining the variance in students' performance ($B = .89$, $\beta = .77$, $t = 17.448$, $p = .001$). The R^2 value (0.606) explained the variance in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. In this case, the variance in students' performance is (60.6%) due to TQM.

Limitation, Suggestions, and Future Research Concerns

The current study has some limitations as this study was conducted in district Lahore tehsil city only. A simple random sampling technique was used for this study. Data was collected from the individuals from public sectors schools from district Lahore, adopted tools were used in this context. It is suggested that other sampling techniques can be used for this future research; the population and sample of the study can be increased based on the type of the research. Future research can be conducted in different districts of Punjab and Pakistan. Experimental quantitative, qualitative and mix-method research can be conducted on the same variables. This research was conducted at the secondary level; in the future, research can be conducted at elementary, primary, higher secondary and higher education levels in the public and private sectors. Future research may also be undertaken on self-structured questionnaires too.

Acknowledgment

Researchers are intensely gratified to ALLAH (سبحان و تعالی) and HAZRAT MUHAMMAD (خاتم النبیین ﷺ) for the completion this study. The researchers are also thankful to parents, honorable and respected teachers and friends for helping and prayers to complete this manuscript.

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Author Information

Muhammad Siddique

Ph. D Scholar Education, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan.

Dr. Ijaz Ahmad Tatlah

Associate Professor, Division of Education, University of Education, Lahore

Dr. Muhammad Shabbir Ali

Associate Professor, Division of Education, University of Education, Lahore

Tajammal Hussain Awan

Ph. D Scholar, Superior University Lahore, Pakistan.

Hamid Ali Nadeem

*Lecturer, Department of Educational Planning, Policy Studies and Leadership
Allama Iqbal Open University, Islamabad*
